

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14980805

Bio-Chemical Hazards And Control Practices Among Non-Healthcare Workers In Tertiary Hospitals In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the bio-chemical hazards among non-health care workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State employing a cross-sectional study design. Data for the study was obtained from a sample size of 656 non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State drawn from the population of 1811 non-healthcare workers in the tertiary hospitals in Rivers State using two-sampling procedure. A validated self-structured questionnaire titled “Bio-chemical Hazards Questionnaire (B-CHQ)” with a reliability index of 0.89 was used for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25 employing both descriptive and inferential statistics of Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, ANCOVA. The study found that the non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals encountered ergonomic hazards such as exposure to residual chemical from cleaning agents (3.10 ± 0.867); chemical poisoning from pesticides (2.98 ± 0.896); hazardous chemicals from improperly disposed medical waste (3.05 ± 0.847); mold, dust mites, or other allergens (2.89 ± 1.030); and exposure to airborne pathogens (3.08 ± 0.872). These hazards differ significantly based on workers age and years of work experience ($P < .05$). The study revealed that the workers had some control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards in hospitals but the practices do not differ based on workers’ gender, age and years of work experience ($P > .05$). Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State encountered various bio-chemical hazards that significantly differs based on age and work experience. They also have control practices implemented which do not significantly differ based gender, age and years of work experience. Finally the study recommended that that tertiary hospitals should implement regular, updated, and comprehensive training programmes on hazard identification, risk assessment, and proper handling of hazardous substances.

Keywords: Bio-chemical Hazards, Non-Healthcare Workers, Tertiary Hospitals

INTRODUCTION

Non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals play a crucial role in maintaining hospital functions, often working behind the scenes in roles such as cleaners, administrative staff, security personnel, and maintenance workers. These individuals contribute significantly to the smooth operation of healthcare facilities (Coutinho, et al., 2018), yet they are often exposed to bio-chemical hazards that can pose serious health risks (Debnath, 2017). Bio-chemical hazards, which encompass both chemical and biological threats, can lead to adverse health outcomes when exposure is not properly controlled. Non-

healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals are at risk of encountering hazardous chemicals, such as cleaning agents and disinfectants, as well as biological agents like bacteria, viruses, and other pathogens present in hospital environments. These hazards pose substantial risks to worker health and safety, especially when protective measures and control practices are insufficient or poorly enforced (Zhou & Guo, 2017). Bio-chemical hazards can be categorized into chemical hazards and biological hazards. Chemical hazards involve exposure to harmful substances that can cause various health issues, such as respiratory problems, skin irritations, and long-term illnesses like cancer. Numerous hazardous chemicals and toxins are present in different workplaces, including environmental smoke, cleaning products, acids, pesticides, carbon monoxide, and flammable liquids. Chemical hazards significantly contribute to occupational hazards among professional workers (Hisam, 2022). Biological hazards on the other hand are living organisms or their by-products that can cause disease. In certain environments, such as farms, zoos, hospitals, medical offices, or veterinary clinics, workers may be exposed to biological health hazards like blood, fungi, mold, viruses, animal droppings, and insect bites (Swiner, 2023).

Bio-chemical hazards in tertiary hospitals are a growing concern, not only due to their immediate harmful effects but also because of their long-term implications on workers' health. Non-healthcare workers in these hospitals are regularly exposed to chemicals, which can lead to both immediate and long-term health effects. For example, exposure to chemicals such as bleach, formaldehyde, and ammonia can cause respiratory issues, skin burns, or other acute symptoms (Virji et al., 2022). Long-term exposure may lead to chronic respiratory diseases or even cancer. Research indicates that improper handling or lack of adequate protective gear significantly increases the likelihood of chemical-related health issues among non-healthcare workers in hospitals (Liu et al., 2019). On the biological side, hospital environments are replete with potential biological hazards, such as bloodborne pathogens, bacteria, and viruses. These agents can cause life-threatening diseases, including hepatitis B and C, HIV, and tuberculosis, making it essential to understand the types of hazards workers are exposed to and the appropriate control measures to mitigate these risks (Zhao et al., 2016). Non-healthcare workers may encounter biological hazards through contact with contaminated surfaces, blood, or waste products. These workers may also be at risk of exposure to airborne pathogens in poorly ventilated areas (Zhou & Guo, 2017). The risk of biological hazard exposure can be particularly high for cleaners and maintenance workers, who are often in direct contact with contaminated materials.

To mitigate the risks associated with bio-chemical hazards, several control practices can be implemented. According to the International Labour Organization [ILO] (2016), control practices involve "a systematic approach to managing health and safety risks by identifying potential hazards, assessing their risks, and implementing measures to eliminate or minimize those risks. In the context of this study control practices refer to the specific measures and strategies implemented to manage and mitigate the various occupational hazards that non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals encounter. These practices are critical in ensuring the safety of non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals.

The use of PPE is essential to protect non-healthcare workers from exposure to both chemical and biological hazards. Properly designed gloves, masks, face shields, and protective clothing are vital in reducing direct exposure to hazardous materials. Studies show that non-healthcare workers who regularly use PPE are at a significantly lower risk of experiencing chemical burns, skin irritations, or respiratory problems (Liu et al., 2019). Ensuring that workers are adequately trained on the correct usage of PPE is equally important to maximize its effectiveness. Regular training on hazard identification, safe handling procedures, and emergency response is critical for non-healthcare workers. Research has shown that workers who are educated about the potential dangers they face are more likely to take appropriate precautions and reduce their risk of exposure (Bodin et al., 2015). Training should focus on proper chemical handling, waste disposal protocols, and infection control practices. Ensuring that hospital environments are properly ventilated is essential to control both chemical and biological hazards. Good ventilation can help to disperse harmful fumes from cleaning agents and reduce the concentration of airborne pathogens. Hospitals should be equipped with high-quality ventilation systems that meet health and safety standards (Zhao et al., 2016). In addition, proper cleaning schedules and waste disposal practices should be enforced to limit the exposure to harmful biological agents. Monitoring workplace

conditions and ensuring that non-healthcare workers adhere to safety protocols is vital for reducing the risk of exposure. Hospitals should establish regular health surveillance programs to monitor the health status of workers and identify potential illnesses that could be linked to bio-chemical hazards. Additionally, compliance with safety regulations, such as those outlined by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), is critical to ensuring that the workplace remains safe (Bodin et al., 2015).

Demographic factors play a crucial role in shaping the bio-chemical hazards faced by non-healthcare workers as well as the control practices they adopt to mitigate these hazards. Age, gender, and years of working experience can influence susceptibility to the hazards. Biologically, age reflects the progressive accumulation of changes in an organism over time, leading to variations in structure and function (Partridge et al., 2018). In the context of the study, age is defined as the chronological categorization of workers based on their duration of life since birth, used as a demographic variable to analyze patterns and trends in exposure to bio-chemical hazards and adherence to control practices. A study by Ahrens et al (2019) found that older employees in physically demanding roles are at a higher risk of hazards compared to their younger counterparts.

Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviors, expressions, and identities of individuals as male, female, or non-binary. It differs from sex, which is biologically determined, and encompasses how individuals perceive themselves and are perceived by society based on cultural norms and expectations (World Health Organization, 2022). In the context of the study, gender is defined as the socially and biologically constructed characteristics and roles typically associated with being male or female, which may influence individuals' exposure to bio-chemical hazards and their engagement in control practices. Regarding the influence of gender on bio-chemical hazards and control practices among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospital, research by Leung et al (2017) indicated that female workers in these roles are more likely to experience chemical-related health issues compared to their male counterparts.

Years of working experience refers to the total duration an individual has spent in active employment, typically measured from the start of their first job to their current role. This variable is often used to assess a worker's level of expertise, familiarity with occupational processes, and exposure to workplace environments (ILO, 2021). In the context of the study, years of working experience is defined as the length of time an individual has been employed in a particular field or job, reflecting their exposure to workplace practices, hazards, and control measures. The study categorizes working experience into (a) Less than 5 years, representing workers at the early stages of their careers, often with limited exposure to occupational risks and control practices; (b) 5–10 years, denoting mid-career workers who may have moderate familiarity with workplace hazards and a growing adherence to safety protocols; and (c) 11 years and above representing seasoned workers with substantial exposure to occupational environments and extensive experience in identifying and managing risks. This categorization enables the study to analyze how years of experience influence the awareness, perception, and implementation of hazard control measures, as well as differences in vulnerability across experience levels (ILO, 2021). Workers with extensive experience may develop strategies to mitigate risks but might also face increased exposure to hazards due to prolonged exposure. Conversely, less experienced workers might lack the knowledge and skills to manage hazards effectively, as noted by Koukoulaki (2018).

In Nigeria, particularly in Rivers State, tertiary hospitals such as the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital (RSUTH) provide specialized medical care and serve as major health centres for the region. Despite the importance of these institutions, the risk of bio-chemical hazards to non-healthcare workers is often underreported and understudied. This is particularly concerning given that workers in non-medical roles may not receive the same level of training or protective equipment as their healthcare counterparts. Many of these workers are routinely exposed to dangerous chemicals, such as disinfectants and cleaning agents, and may unknowingly come into contact with biological agents through routine tasks such as cleaning patient rooms or handling waste, yet there is little information available regarding the prevalence and management of these hazards. Existing studies have mainly focused on healthcare workers, who are more directly involved with patient care, leaving a gap in our understanding of the hazards faced by

workers in non-medical roles. Furthermore, there is a lack of research on the specific control practices that are in place for non-healthcare workers in the region, making it difficult to assess the adequacy of current safety measures. The few existing studies often focus on isolated aspects of hospital safety, without considering the comprehensive nature of bio-chemical hazard exposure across different worker groups. This gap is particularly concerning given the growing number of tertiary hospitals in the state and the increasing use of hazardous chemicals and biological agents in hospital settings.

This study aims to fill this gap by examining the bio-chemical hazards that non-healthcare workers are exposed to in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. It will assess current control practices, identify areas for improvement, and provide recommendations for enhancing the health and safety of non-healthcare workers in the region.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the bio-chemical hazards affecting non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State?
2. What are the control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State?
3. What are the differences in bio-chemical hazards encountered among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience?
4. What are the differences in control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. There is no significant difference in bio-chemical hazards encountered among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience.
2. There is no significant difference in control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The sample size for the study was 656 non-healthcare workers drawn from the population of 1811 non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State (Opadeyi et al., 2018; Ugwu, 2023; Devex, 2023). The sample size was selected using two sampling procedures proportionate stratified random sampling technique and purposive sampling technique.

The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Bio-Chemical Hazards Questionnaire (B-CHQ)" with a reliability index of 0.89. The instrument was composed of two sections (A, and B). Section A consists of demographic variables which included gender, age and years of experience. Section B consists of items which addressed the bio-chemical hazards the non-healthcare workers are exposed to. These items were structured in a 4-point likert format of "Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree" respectively. The data for the study were collected through the administration of the instrument on 656 respondents drawn from the tertiary institutions. This was achieved by obtaining an introductory letter from the Head of Department which was presented to the Director of Administration of each of the tertiary hospital who approved the visiting and ensured the cooperation of the staff. The data collection was done by the researcher with the help of trained research assistants and a return rate of 98.5% was achieved. An ethical clearance was obtain from University of Port Harcourt, University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH/ADM/90/S.11/VOLXI/17013) and Rivers State University Teaching Hospital Research Ethics Committee (RSUTH/REC/2024/572) to conduct the study in the selected hospitals.

The completed copies of the questionnaire were collated, coded and analyzed using the statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. Descriptive statistics of percentage was used to analyse the demographic variables, Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics of ANCOVA were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demography	Cohorts	F	%
Gender	Female	350	54.2
	Male	296	45.8
	Total	646	100.0
Age	Less than 30years	143	22.1
	30-39yrs	302	46.8
	40years and Above	201	31.1
	Total	646	100.0
Years of Working Experience	Less than 5years	200	31.0
	5-10years	229	35.4
	11years and Above	217	33.6
	Total	646	100.0

Results in Table 1 showed that majority 350(54.2%) of the non-healthcare workers were female, between the age range of 30-39 years (46.8%, representing early to mid-career stages, known for high productivity and active work engagement) and have had 5–10 years of experience (indicating mid-career familiarity with occupational hazards but potential complacency with safety).

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation analysis on bio-chemical hazards encountered by non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State

	Bio-chemical Hazards	Mean	St. D	Decision
1	Exposure to viruses, bacteria, or other pathogens through contact with contaminated surfaces, documents, or from interaction with sick colleagues.	2.16	.994	Rejected
2	Expose to mold, dust mites, or other allergens, potentially causing respiratory issues or aggravating conditions like asthma.	2.89	1.030	Accepted
3	Exposure to infectious diseases when handling contaminated laundry, bed linens and patient gowns, without adequate protective measures.	2.97	1.028	Accepted
4	Risk of needle-stick injuries and infections from used needles and syringes	2.09	.980	Rejected
5	Exposure to blood and other bodily fluids while cleaning patient areas, which leads a significant risk of transmitting bloodborne pathogens such as HIV and hepatitis B and C.	2.03	1.027	Rejected
6	Exposed to airborne pathogens in hospital environments, which can cause respiratory infections and other airborne diseases.	3.08	.872	Accepted
7	Exposure to residual chemicals from cleaning agents used in the office environment that may cause respiratory irritation, skin sensitivity, or allergic reactions.	3.10	.867	Accepted
8	Exposure to chemical substances found in toner, ink, and the fumes they emit.	2.24	1.321	Rejected
9	Exposure to chemical poisoning from pesticides used for pest control in the hospital environment.	2.98	.896	Accepted
10	Exposure to hazardous chemicals from improperly disposed of medical waste, including chemotherapy drugs	3.05	.847	Accepted
11	Risk of developing asthma and other respiratory conditions from handling of chemicals used to sanitize the hospital environment.	3.01	.887	Accepted
12	Exposure to mercury from medical equipment (such as broken thermometers), leading to neurological and kidney damage.	3.00	.960	Accepted
	Aggregate	2.71	0.976	Accepted

Table 2 revealed that with an aggregate mean value of 2.71 ± 0.976 , the non-healthcare workers accepted that they do encounter bio-chemical hazards in course of their work. The result revealed that the bio-chemical hazards encountered by the non-healthcare workers include: exposure to residual chemical from cleaning agents (3.10 ± 0.867); exposure to chemical poisoning from pesticides (2.98 ± 0.896); exposure from hazardous chemicals from improperly disposed medical waste (3.05 ± 0.847); exposure from handling of chemicals used to sanitize the hospital environment (3.10 ± 0.887) exposure to mercury from medical equipment (3.00 ± 0.960); exposure to mold, dust mites, or other allergens (2.89 ± 1.030); exposure to infectious diseases (2.97 ± 1.028) and exposure to airborne pathogens (3.08 ± 0.872).

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation analysis on control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State

	Bio-chemical Hazards Control Practices	Mean	St. D	Decision
12	Comprehensive training for all staff on the safe handling, storage, and disposal of chemicals.	2.38	.772	Rejected
13	Substitute hazardous chemicals with less harmful alternatives (environmentally friendly products) whenever possible.	3.06	.987	Accepted
14	Enforce safe work practices and procedures, such as adherence to safety guidelines.	3.41	.885	Accepted
15	Implementation of strict infection control measures, including hand hygiene and use of antiseptics.	2.40	.761	Rejected
16	Perform routine health screenings for early detection of infectious diseases	3.35	.861	Accepted
17	Attend training on hazards management techniques and strategies to cope with occupational hazards.	3.39	.926	Accepted
	Aggregate	2.99	0.865	Accepted

Table 3 revealed that with an aggregate mean value of 2.99 ± 0.865 , the non-healthcare workers accepted that there are control practices they do implemented to mitigate occupational hazards encounter during the course of their work. The control measure implement by the non-healthcare workers include: substitute hazardous chemicals with less harmful alternatives (3.06 ± 0.987); enforcement of safe work practices and procedures (3.41 ± 0.885); performing routine health screenings (3.35 ± 0.81) and attending training on hazards management techniques (3.39 ± 0.926).

Table 4: ANCOVA analysis on difference in difference in bio-chemical hazards encountered among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience.

Dependent Variable: Bio-Chemical Hazards

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	12.259 ^a	17	.721	3.826	.000
Intercept	2785.348	1	2785.348	14776.913	.000
Gender	.071	1	.071	.378	.539
Age	3.606	2	1.803	9.565	.000
Work Experience	1.496	2	.748	3.967	.019
Gender * Age	.574	2	.287	1.522	.219
Gender * Work Experience	.198	2	.099	.525	.592
Age * Work Experience	5.302	4	1.326	7.032	.000
Gender * age * Work Experience	.281	4	.070	.373	.828
Error	118.374	628	.188		
Total	5085.000	646			
Corrected Total	130.633	645			

***a. R Squared = .094 (Adjusted R Squared = .069)**

Table 4 revealed that the overall model was statistically significant ($F = 3.826$, $p = .000$), and it explained a significant portion of the variance in bio-chemical ($R\text{-squared} = .094$). The main effects of age ($F = 9.565$, $p = .000$), and years of work experience ($F = 3.967$, $p = .019$) were found to be significant, indicating that these variables had individual difference in the bio-chemical hazards encountered by the workers while main gender ($F = 0.378$, $p = .539$), indicated no significant difference. Also, the interactive effects of age and years of work experience ($F = 7.032$, $p = .000$) was significant.

Table 5: ANCOVA analysis on difference in control practices implemented to mitigate bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State based on age, gender and years of work experience.

Dependent Variable: Bio-Chemical Hazards Control Practices					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	2.286 ^a	17	.134	1.319	.174
Intercept	3178.730	1	3178.730	31182.218	.000
Gender	.197	1	.197	1.937	.164
Age	.061	2	.031	.300	.741
Work Experience	.540	2	.270	2.647	.072
Gender * Age	.135	2	.067	.660	.517
Gender * Work Experience	.208	2	.104	1.020	.361
Age * Work Experience	.535	4	.134	1.313	.264
Gender * age * Work Experience	.538	4	.135	1.320	.261
Error	64.019	628	.102		
Total	5620.901	646			
Corrected Total	66.305	645			

Table 5 revealed that the overall model was not statistically significant ($F = 1.319$, $p = .174$). The main effects of gender ($F = 1.937$, $p = 0.164$), age ($F = 0.300$, $p = .741$), and years of work experience ($F = 2.647$, $p = .072$) were found not to be significant, indicating that these variables had no individual difference in the bio-chemical hazards encountered by the workers

DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents an analysis of biochemical hazards encountered by non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State. The findings, with an aggregate mean value of 2.99 ± 0.856 suggest that these workers encounter significant bio-chemical hazards in their work environments. Table 4 reveals that demographic factors such as gender, age, and years of work experience significantly influence the exposure to bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers.

These findings align with the study by Achalu (2019), which emphasizes that exposure to toxic chemicals, fumes, and gases in workplaces can result in acute and chronic health complications, including respiratory issues, skin conditions, and even poisoning. It is also consistent with Ndejjo et al. (2015), who found that hospital cleaning staff exposed to cleaning chemicals reported higher incidences of respiratory symptoms and skin conditions. Similarly, Smedley et al. (2019) noted that healthcare settings often expose workers to chemical hazards, leading to both acute conditions, such as eye and respiratory irritation, and chronic effects like asthma and dermatitis. This aligns with the finding of this study that chemical agents used for cleaning and sanitization pose significant risks. Moreover, De Souza Pereira et al. (2022) identified exposure to chemical agents as a key occupational hazard for hospital cleaning staff, underlining the precarious working conditions of these workers, especially when safety protocols are inadequately enforced. World Health Organization (2016) also highlighted the risks that technical support staff in laboratories face, particularly the potential for exposure to bloodborne pathogens. This is similar to the findings in the study by Rymer et al. (2016), which observed that non-clinical healthcare personnel are often exposed to infectious agents, especially through accidents involving sharps or improperly disposed medical waste.

Doss, Amirthalingam, and Kathiresan (2023) study also found that housekeeping staff in hospitals were particularly vulnerable to biological hazards, including exposure to infectious diseases, a risk confirmed by 31% of the participants in their study. Adebayo et al. (2020) study on occupational hazards in healthcare settings also found that improper chemical handling practices and insufficient PPE usage were major contributors to health risks among non-clinical staff. Their findings also emphasized that mercury exposure, particularly from broken medical equipment, remains a persistent issue in many hospitals, similar to the present study's results.

Adewale and Olaleye (2020) in their study also found that maintenance workers in Nigerian tertiary hospitals face substantial chemical exposure, particularly from cleaning agents. Similarly, Zhao and Wang (2015) identified chemical exposure as a major concern for non-healthcare workers, particularly due to cleaning agents and improper workplace ergonomics, leading to respiratory and dermatological conditions. These findings are consistent with the results in this study, where workers experienced health problems such as skin irritation and respiratory issues from chemicals. The study by Khan and Ali (2018) further supports these findings, revealing high levels of exposure to toxic chemicals among cleaning and maintenance staff in Pakistan, where inadequate personal protective equipment (PPE) was a major contributing factor. This is mirrored in the current study, where workers identified chemical hazards, including exposure to chemicals from improperly disposed medical waste, as a significant concern. Inadequate PPE and lack of proper safety measures were also identified in the study by Okeke and Nwankwo (2019), which similarly pointed out the high chemical exposure risks among maintenance and cleaning personnel in Nigerian hospitals.

However, some studies do not entirely support the findings of this study. Osei-Bonsu et al. (2021) study for example, reported that chemical hazards were less frequent in healthcare settings where structured training and routine hazard management practices were implemented. Their study, conducted in Ghana, highlighted the effectiveness of systematic safety protocols in reducing exposure among non-healthcare workers. This contrasts with the findings of this present study, suggesting gaps in the enforcement of safety measures in the Nigerian context. Smedley et al. (2019) study also found that the risks associated with chemical exposure in healthcare settings, while present, were often mitigated by better control measures and regular training for staff. Chinwe and Eze (2019), which focused on non-healthcare workers in Nigerian hospitals, found that while exposure to biological hazards was recognized, it was not as prominent as other hazards such as physical or chemical risks. The study did not report as high an incidence of exposure to infectious diseases or airborne pathogens as observed in this study. Similarly, a study by Okeke and Nwankwo (2019) noted biological risks but did not emphasize airborne pathogens to the extent that the current study does.

The findings from Table 4 suggest that the overall model was statistically significant ($F = 3.826$, $p = .000$), which indicates that the factors under study namely, age, years of work experience, and gender, have a noteworthy impact on the bio-chemical hazards encountered by non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals. The model explained a significant portion of the variance in bio-chemical hazard exposure ($R\text{-squared} = .094$), which highlights the relevance of the predictors under examination in understanding the exposure risks for non-healthcare workers.

The results showed that age ($F = 9.565$, $p = .000$) and years of work experience ($F = 3.967$, $p = .019$) were statistically significant in influencing the bio-chemical hazards encountered by non-healthcare workers. This suggests that workers' age and their experience in the field significantly affect their exposure to hazardous bio-chemical agents in the workplace. The finding on age supports previous studies that suggest older workers may have different risk perceptions or more cautious behaviour regarding bio-chemical exposures due to accumulated knowledge or the wear and tear of their health over time (Sibille et al., 2018). Additionally, older workers may also have more years of experience, which can influence their awareness and handling of hazards (Rao et al., 2020).

The effect of years of work experience aligns with literature that finds experienced workers tend to have a better understanding of the risks in their working environment and may adopt safer work practices. This was similarly observed by Wang et al. (2019), who found that workers with more years of experience were more likely to adhere to safety protocols and use personal protective equipment (PPE)

more diligently, thus reducing their exposure to bio-chemical hazards. Conversely, Jin et al. (2017) reported that although more experienced workers may be more knowledgeable about safety practices, their familiarity with certain tasks could lead to complacency, increasing the risk of exposure.

However, studies such as Salminen et al. (2018) suggested that despite extensive work experience, older employees may face health risks due to cumulative exposure over time, which may lead to long-term health problems such as respiratory diseases or skin conditions. This is significant in understanding the heightened risks faced by non-healthcare workers in hospital settings, especially for those who have been working in such environments for an extended period.

The main effect of gender ($F = 0.378$, $p = .539$) was found to be insignificant, which suggests that gender does not significantly influence the exposure to bio-chemical hazards among non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals. This finding is somewhat unexpected, as previous studies have highlighted the role of gender in occupational health risks. For example, Zhao et al. (2017) observed that women in certain hospital roles, especially those involved in cleaning and waste disposal, were more likely to suffer from chemical-induced asthma or dermatitis due to the chemical agents they used. On the other hand, Kumar et al. (2019) suggested that gender might not be a direct determinant of risk but rather interacts with other factors such as job roles, working hours, and the use of personal protective equipment.

Several studies coincide with the findings of this research, particularly those that emphasise the influence of age and work experience on workers' exposure to occupational hazards. For example, Sibille et al. (2018) and Rao et al. (2020) both highlight that older workers and those with more years of experience tend to be more aware of hazards and better at managing risks. This is in agreement with the current study's finding that age and years of work experience significantly influence bio-chemical hazard exposure.

However, the finding on gender contradicts some previous studies, such as Zhao et al. (2017), who found gender-specific differences in exposure to bio-chemical hazards, especially among female cleaning staff. It is possible that the type of work or the hospital's safety protocols in the current study's setting may have lessened gender disparities. The lack of a significant gender effect in this study calls for more in-depth exploration of how different hospital roles and gender may interact to impact hazard exposure, as indicated by studies like Kumar et al. (2019), who pointed out that gender could influence the risk depending on specific occupational roles.

Table 3 highlights that non-healthcare workers in the tertiary hospitals under study acknowledge the importance of control measures to mitigate bio-chemical hazards. The average score of 2.99 ± 0.865 reflects a general consensus among workers that these control practices are being actively implemented in their work environments. While the implementation of control practices appears to be widespread, Table 5 reveals that demographic factors such as gender, age, and years of work experience did not significantly influence the adoption of control practices among non-healthcare workers.

The findings from this study both align with and contradict existing literature on the implementation of safety measures and the impact of demographic variables. The consistent use of control practices by non-healthcare workers aligns with previous research that stresses the importance of safety protocols, training, and regular health screenings in reducing chemical exposure in healthcare settings (Munjil et al., 2018; Montalbano et al., 2019). Additionally, the finding that gender does not significantly influence hazard exposure contrasts with studies that have found gender-based differences in exposure levels, particularly in cleaning roles (Zhao et al., 2017).

The lack of significant findings related to age and experience also offers a different perspective from previous studies, such as those by Sibille et al. (2018), which suggested that older workers are more susceptible to health risks due to prolonged exposure. This difference may reflect the uniformity of safety protocols in the hospitals studied, which could have reduced any potential disparities related to workers' demographic characteristics.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that non-healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Rivers State face bio-chemical hazards such as exposure to residual chemical from cleaning agents; exposure to chemical poisoning from pesticides; exposure from hazardous chemicals from improperly disposed medical waste; exposure from handling of chemicals used to sanitize the hospital environment; exposure to mercury from medical equipment; exposure to mold, dust mites, or other allergens; exposure to infectious diseases and exposure to airborne pathogens. These hazards significantly differs based on the workers age and years of work experience. Control practices such as substituting hazardous chemicals with less harmful alternatives; enforcement of safe work practices and procedures; performing routine health screenings and attending training on hazards management techniques were implemented by the workers to mitigate the bio-chemical risks but the control practices do not significantly differ based on their gender, age and years of work experience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Regular, updated, and comprehensive training programmes on hazard identification, risk assessment, and proper handling of hazardous substances are implemented in tertiary hospitals.
2. Hospital management should take proactive steps to evaluate the efficacy of these substitutions and safe work practices by conducting regular safety audits and hazard assessments.
3. Tertiary hospitals should introduce more comprehensive occupational health surveillance programs that go beyond general screenings and focus specifically on potential exposure to hazardous chemicals, infectious diseases, and other environmental factors.

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